

Designing assessments for large university classes: Considering Artificial Intelligence, Academic Integrity and Bloom's Revised Taxonomy

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Abstract

This article seeks to report on the design and assessment of an undergraduate module in developmental psychology, as delivered to a cohort of 500+ students. This module is positioned in year one of an initial teacher education programme in an Irish university. Although this module had been delivered across preceding years, the surge in use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) amongst university students served as a catalyst for reconsidering the selected mode of assessment. During module design, the lecturer placed particular emphasis on ensuring the chosen assessment promoted broad levels of student learning across all domains of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy of Educational Objectives (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001), whilst minimising the potential threats of AI to academic integrity. Based on a review of students' in-class attendance, online engagement, and performance in the terminal examination, strengths and limitations of the module and chosen assessment are acknowledged, with reference to implications for practice in the large class context.

Keywords: *Bloom's Revised Taxonomy; Artificial Intelligence; academic integrity; large class sizes; assessment; teacher education.*

1. Introduction

Over recent years, the rapid growth of technology, particularly in terms of Artificial Intelligence (AI), has transformed daily life, including across the educational domain (Evangelista, 2025; Uunona & Goosen, 2023). On one hand, the strengths of AI cannot be denied, including enhanced personalised learning, automated routine tasks, and the provision of instant feedback to students (Halaweh, 2023; Sok & Heng, 2023). In contrast, the growth in AI usage in education raises significant challenges and concerns, not least in relation to threatening academic integrity. In particular, the misuse of AI can undermine the very purpose of education, where AI-assisted tools, such as essay generators and automated problem-solvers, can threaten students' understanding, learning, creativity and critical thinking (Ellison & Patel, 2022; Yunus Basha, 2024). As stated by Ateeq et al., (2024, p.1), "As AI tools become increasingly sophisticated, so too does the potential for students to utilize these technologies to gain undue advantages in their academic pursuits".

Reflecting on this issue, educators are now forced to critically consider module design and delivery, including the selection and creation of assessments. This matter is even more pertinent when considering large class sizes, where research highlights that such classes are often taught entirely in lecture mode, often leading to a lack of engagement between faculty members and students, a lack of teaching strategies employed to develop higher-order thinking skills, and a reduction in deep learning and critical thinking for students (Cooper & Robinson, 2000; DeRuisseau, 2016; Kuh et al., 1991). Research also shows that assessments employed in large group classes often call for low levels of student understanding (Cooper & Robinson, 2000). Concerningly, Evangelista (2025) argues that such assessments are particularly vulnerable to AI-generated content, as tools like ChatGPT can easily replicate recall and basic comprehension tasks. In contrast, assessments that focus on higher-order cognitive skills, such as the analysis of complex problems, the evaluation of different perspectives, and the creation of original work, are less vulnerable to the powers of AI. Taken together, this research points to the pressing need for educators to employ more engaging learning methodologies in large group lectures, coupled with assessments that call for broad and deep levels of student learning and understanding, with due regard for the correct usage of AI in higher education.

1.1. Bloom's Revised Taxonomy of Educational Objectives

Reflecting on the spectrum of cognitive objectives, *Bloom's Revised Taxonomy of Educational Objectives* (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001) deserves attention. This taxonomy moves from lower-order cognitive processes to higher-order processes, spanning *remembering, understanding, applying, analysing, evaluating* and *creating*. Griffin (2020) argues that the concept of 'deep' and 'surface' level learning can be mapped directly onto this framework, where careful consideration of the framework can support the

maximisation of students’ learning across cognitive domains. Moreover, Evangelista (2025) argues that assessments selected towards the higher levels of Bloom’s Taxonomy foster deeper learning and strengthen academic integrity. Table 1 presents an overview of the structure of the cognitive process dimensions of the revised taxonomy, as sourced from Griffin (2020, pp. 2 - 3) and adapted from Krathwohl (2002).

Table 1. Structure of the cognitive process dimension of Bloom’s Revised Taxonomy, as sourced from Griffin (2020, pp. 2 – 3) and adapted from Krathwohl (2002)

1. Remember	Retrieving relevant knowledge from long-term memory	1.1 Recognizing 1.2 Recalling
2. Understand	Determining the meaning of instructional messages, including oral, written, and graphic communication	2.1 Interpreting 2.2 Exemplifying 2.3 Classifying 2.4 Summarizing 2.5 Inferring 2.6 Comparing 2.7 Explaining
3. Apply	Carrying out or using a procedure in a given situation.	3.1 Executing 3.2 Implementing
4. Analyze	Breaking material into its constituent parts and detecting how the parts relate to one another and to an overall structure or purpose.	4.1 Differentiating 4.2 Organizing 4.3 Attributing
5. Evaluate	Making judgments based on criteria and standards.	5.1 Checking 5.2 Critiquing
6. Create	Putting elements together to form a novel, coherent whole or make an original product.	6.1 Generating 6.2 Planning 6.3 Producing

With regard to large class sizes, research highlights that class size can significantly affect the level of cognitive skills used by students in the classroom. Citing over 30 years of research, Cuseo (1997) emphasises how large class settings reduce students’ depth of thinking, such that the discourse of students who participate in large classes most often reflects the lowest level of thinking on Bloom’s taxonomy, i.e. factual recall. Reflecting on such data, the following section details the design of an undergraduate module in Developmental Psychology, with due regard for optimising students’ learning across

Bloom's Revised Taxonomy, whilst mitigating against the potential negative impact of AI on academic integrity.

2. Description of the Teaching/Learning Context

This module was designed and delivered to a cohort of over 500 students undertaking an undergraduate degree in Education in an Irish university. This module is positioned in the first semester of students' programme, aimed at providing students with foundational knowledge and understanding of how to support children and their development. The module places emphasis on the child as learner, with due regard for the unique role of the teacher in providing for the holistic development of children. In particular, the module seeks to enable student teachers to understand and critique current thinking on human development and learning, with a specific focus on relevant theories of child development and learning. Over the course of the module, students are introduced to a range of theories and frameworks of child development and learning, alongside the application of such theories to practice.

This module was ascribed three European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits, comprising two 45-minute lectures, delivered weekly to students in groups of 170+. This totalled to 24 contact hours for students over a 12-week semester, and a total of 72 lecturer contact hours. Students were also required to devote an additional three private study hours weekly to the module across the semester. This section should provide a clear description of the teaching context, including the nature/profile of the class, the number of students and the teaching strategies/approaches in use, and challenges for teaching and learning. All texts, figures and tables must be included within the document margins.

3. Assessment Strategies

Over previous iterations of the module, the lecturer had employed various assessment strategies aimed at promoting students' learning across multiple levels of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). In the most recent years, students have been presented with case study data, which described a child in middle childhood, with reference to cognitive, physical, social and emotional development. Based on the presented data, students were required to devise three strategies to support the child's learning and development in the classroom, with reference to at least two domains of child development. Marking criteria spanned four domains, including (a) Depth of knowledge & understanding of psychological theory, with evidence of critical thinking, (b) Application of theory to practice, (c) Evidence of engagement with cutting-edge literature, and (d) Structure, organisation, and adherence to academic and linguistic conventions.

Although this mode of assessment had proven quite effective in previous years, the surge in use of AI amongst university students now poses a strong potential threat to the academic integrity of students' responses. Moreover, although tools such as Turnitin can help to support the detection of plagiarism and safeguard the uniqueness of students' work, an array of studies have now shown that AI tools' ability to generate human-like text is reducing the precision rate of AI-powered tools in accurately detecting AI-generated material (Ladha et al., 2023; Malik & Amjad, 2025). In light of this, the lecturer decided to opt for the more traditional end-of-semester examination, such that students would not have access to any technology during the formal assessment time.

Table 2 presents an overview of the assessment strategies employed across the module. Column 1 names each assessment strategy, with an explanation of the same outlined in Column 2. In Column 3, the assessment strategy is then mapped onto the relevant cognitive process dimensions of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Notably, given the three-ECTS credits associated with this module, only one form of graded assessment was permitted, whereby formative assessment strategies had to remain supportive in nature. Accordingly, assessment strategies 1 and 2 in Table 2 did not form part of students' final grade. Rather, the summative end-of-semester examination (strategy 3) formed the full weighting of students' final grade. Much attention was given to the careful design of this examination, with due regard for assessing students' learning across multiple levels of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy. Accordingly, each of the three sub-sections of the examination is detailed below. Finally, during the examination, students were provided with separate question and answer booklets. The answer booklet had a predefined writing space for each response, where students were informed that any information written beyond the lines would not be graded. This was to support clarity and conciseness in students' answers, given that students had 120 minutes of examination time, and given that one lecturer was tasked with marking the 500+ examinations in a short timeframe. Table 2 is presented below, with the related grading rubric presented thereafter in Table 3.

Table 2. Assessment strategies employed across the module and their alignment with the cognitive process dimensions of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001)

Assessment strategy and explanation	Explanation of assessment	Alignment with the Cognitive Process Dimensions of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy
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1. Weekly online self-assessment quizzes	These comprised multiple-choice questions and short answers, with instant online feedback.	1. Remember 2. Understand
2. In-class 'Active Student Responding' techniques, as sourced from Griffin & Ryan (2016).	These were conducted on an individual and paired basis in class. Examples included action responses, think-write-pair-share, creation of concept maps, written responses, oral responses, etc.	1. Remember 2. Understand 3. Apply 4. Analyze
3. End of semester exam Part A: 15 multiple-choice questions	These multiple-choice questions were similar to those undertaken by students online across the semester. Three marks were assigned to each question, totalling a maximum of 45 marks.	1. Remember 2. Understand
3. End of semester exam Part B: 10 short answers	Students were provided with ten questions, each presenting some brief child-related data. Students were required to respond to the data, outlining a theory-based strategy that could be used to support the child in question. Three marks were assigned to each answer, totaling to a maximum of 30 marks.	1. Remember 2. Understand 3. Apply 4. Analyze
3. End of semester exam Part C: Case study	Students were presented with comprehensive case study data, detailing 'Sophie', an 8-year-old girl in primary school, with reference to her strengths and needs across the four domains of development: physical, cognitive, social and emotional. Students were required to devise three strategies to support Sophie's learning and development in the classroom, with reference to appropriate psychological theories.	1. Remember 2. Understand 3. Apply 4. Analyze 6. Create

A maximum of 25 marks was assigned to
the overall case study.

Table 3: Grading rubric for end-of-semester examination (summative assessment)

Sub-sections of the examination	Marks awarded					
	0	1	2	3	4	5
<p>Section A: Multiple Choice Questions</p> <p>15 questions @ 3 marks per question. Total 45 marks</p>	incorrect			correct		
<p>Section B: Short Answers</p> <p>10 questions @ 3 marks per question. Total 30 marks.</p>	poor	satisfactory	good	excellent		
<p>Section C: Case study</p> <p>1 question @ 25 marks</p> <p>8 marks per strategy (x3 strategies) and one potential 'bonus' point thereafter: see below. Total 25 marks.</p> <p>Name of strategy (1 mark)</p> <p>Name of related psychological theory (1 mark)</p>	poor	appropriate answer				
	poor	appropriate answer				

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Name of related theorist (1 mark)	poor	appropriate answer				
Details of strategy, showing depth of knowledge and application of theory to practice (5 marks)	unsatisfactory	poor	satisfactory	good	very good	excellent
Variety in developmental domains and theories presented across the three chosen strategies (1 mark)	poor	very good - excellent				

4. Findings and Implications for Practice

To support critical reflection on the strengths and limitations of this module and, particularly, the assessment strategies chosen, module-level data were reviewed. Firstly, attendance data from weekly lectures was extremely high, with an average of over 90% attendance across the module. Online engagement was also comparably high, with over 92% of students logging in weekly to the online learning platform and engaging in each weekly quiz at least once. Moreover, an increase in repeat student engagement in online quizzes was observed towards the end of the semester, whereby students reported using the online quizzes as a means of revision and self-assessment prior to the exam. It must be noted, however, that although students did not receive marks for module attendance, there was potential for students to lose up to 10% of their overall marks for poor in-person attendance or online engagement. As a result, it is impossible to determine whether high module attendance and online engagement were directly linked to students' levels of engagement and motivation, or rather, an outcome of students' concerns of losing marks. Nonetheless, informal feedback from students pointed to the strengths of the online quizzes and the in-class formative assessment strategies in supporting module engagement and learning, as well as preparing them for the different cognitive dimensions within the exam.

Secondly, students' performance in the terminal exam was reviewed, with due regard for the three sub-sections of the exam paper. As previously outlined, Part A comprised 15 MCQ questions, drawing on the *remembering* and *understanding* domains of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). Part B comprised 10 short answers, drawing on the *remembering*, *understanding*, *applying* and *analysing* domains of the taxonomy. Part C comprised a comprehensive case study, drawing on the previous four domains of the taxonomy, as well as *creating*. Given the discretion that pertains to students' exam results, observations regarding general student trends will be reported.

Overall, a review of students' responses highlighted high levels of student *recall* and *understanding* across all module material, which was evident in students' performance across the three sub-sections of the exam. Students' recollection of core material concerning the theories of child development was very good, where the main learning objectives of the module were clearly achieved. Thereafter, an analysis of students' responses across Part B and C of the exam gave insight into students' ability to *analyse* and *apply* the theories to practice. In general, students showed very good capacity in this regard, where they carefully considered the presented child-related data and outlined very appropriate theory-based strategies to support the child's development across the relevant domains. Finally, in Part C of the exam, the breadth of students' learning across five of the six cognitive domains was called into question, including that of *create*. Weighted at 25% of the overall exam, Part C gave excellent insight into the depth of students' learning over the module, with varying performance in students' responses. In general, students' ability to make links between the developmental theories and classroom practices was strong. High performing students were particularly skilled at presenting strategies that integrated multiple psychological theories, where they showed depth and creativity in applying theory to practice. In contrast, some other students' responses were more superficial in nature, where their answers were directly sourced from lecture content. Although this showed students' ability to *recall* the module material and *apply* it to the case study in question, their ability to draw on higher-order cognitive skills, such as *analysing* and *creating*, was reduced. Nonetheless, variance in student performance across a large class cohort is an expected trend, and overall, the mean performance of students in the examination was very assuring, reflecting a wide range of learning across lower and higher-order cognitive domains. Additionally, the selection of the terminal examination guaranteed that students' final assessment was not influenced by AI and that academic integrity was maintained. Moreover, the use of the answer booklet and pre-defined spaces for students to document their answers enhanced clarity and conciseness in students' responses. When combined with the marking rubric, this also greatly supported the grading process, both in terms of accuracy and pace for the marker.

Although the design and assessment of this module posed a range of positives, the drawbacks of the module must be acknowledged. Firstly, the level of planning and background organisation that was required for the module cannot be overlooked, which resulted in a high lecturer workload. In particular, the inclusion of the online weekly quizzes and in-class active student responding activities added to the planning and preparation required. Secondly, although the lecturer focused strongly on maintaining academic integrity and reducing the influence of AI on the terminal exam, the potential for incorporating any of the positive benefits of AI into the module was not explored. Moving forward, this presents as an area for reflection, such that greater balance could potentially be found between availing of the benefits of AI (for lecturers and students alike), whilst maintaining academic integrity in the assessment. Moving forward, the lecturer advocates for greater enactment of the principles of scaffolding theory (Van de Pol, Volman & Beishuizen, 2010); specifically, higher levels of fading of lecturer support over the module and greater transference of responsibility to the learners, particularly by harnessing the benefits that technology can pose.

On reflection, it is clear that a range of strengths and limitations pertained to the design and assessment of this large undergraduate module. Moving forward, it is recommended that those teaching large classes in higher education continue to reflect on the strengths and limitations that AI can pose for module design and assessment, and ensure that teaching, learning and assessment strategies are targeted at both lower and higher-order dimensions of Bloom's Revised Taxonomy, with due regard for maintaining academic integrity in the process. In particular, a return to a carefully crafted traditional examination deserves consideration, with the overall aim of benefiting all learners within large classes.

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